

Advancing agriculture for global food security and prosperity in a changing world

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Abstract:

The rapid rise in population, global climate change and advancements in science and technology, have brought great transformations, around the globe, in recent years. The worldwide food losses and the mounting demands for food have pressurized the means of production viz. agriculture and related sectors. Food is the basic necessity for survival and is a fundamental right of every human. Nutritious food at an optimum level ensures good health, better development and all-around welfare. A food-secure world is unthinkable without the advancement of agriculture. This is achievable through technological interventions like mechanization, digitalization, sustainable intensification, use of biotechnology, adoption of suitable cultivars, integrated pest and disease management, innovative soil and water conservation measures etc. In addition, inspiring people to produce their own food, granting subsidies through policy reforms, encouraging more specialized research and apt technological dissemination would be vital for ensuring a hunger-free world.

Keywords

Advancement, Agriculture, Climate change, Food security, Sustainability

1. Introduction:

The world, at present, has become a dynamic and complex space. A great many challenges loom across the globe ranging from diseases to wars and violence to hunger. The rapid evolution of science and technology has shown some signs to resolve these misfortunes. The question of food security arises almost instantly when one talks about major world issues. And it is certainly a problem, needing a great deal of effort and skills to address.

We, humans, are familiar with agriculture for thousands of years. It has been the major source of food and goods since early civilizations. The agricultural revolution that started 13,000 years back has brought some radical transformations in our living standards (Montgomery, 2007). Despite its long history and meteoric evolution, agriculture, at present, is unable to supply the optimum level of food for the growing population (standing at 7.9 billion.) Malnutrition and hunger persist throughout the world. It is estimated that nearly 795 million people are hungry worldwide and over two billion suffer from micronutrient deficiencies. On the contrary, an equal number i.e. around 2 billions peoples are obese. These figures indicate a disparity in food distribution around the globe (Fan & Rue, 2020).

The world population would likely exceed 9 billion by 2050. It is not easy to feed the growing world population by maintaining the standards since the resources are constantly diminishing (Cole et al., 2018). The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), has predicted the agricultural demand to increase over 50% by 2050 AD (FAO, 2017; FAO, 2018). Goal 2 of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) established by the United Nations in 2015 aims to "End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture." It looks remote, considering the current deterrents such as climatic adversities, rapid population growth, conflicts and slowdown of economic development. In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic has pushed the situation to dire straits (FAO, 2021).

Food security is a condition in which all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to safe, sufficient and nutritious food which meets their dietary requirements and also their food preferences for active and healthy living (FAO, 2018). FAO has set four pillars for food security. These are availability, accessibility, utilization and stability of food (FAO, 2009). In absence of food security, the condition of food insecurity prevails which could lead to malnourishment (deficiencies, excesses or imbalances in a person's intake of food and nutrients.) Food comes from agriculture and we can't imagine food security without the advancement of agriculture.

UN reported Southern Asia and sub-Saharan Africa as the regions with the greatest number of undernourished people (over 500 million) representing the gravest state of food insecurity. 144 million children (under 5) were affected by stunting in 2019, which could have been prevented with a proper supply of nutritious food. This is where the question of advancing agriculture

arises. Agriculture productivity must be increased rapidly in these regions if we are to save these people dying of hunger and malnutrition.

2. Challenges to food security

Global food security is threatened by multiple factors in recent times. Climate change, overpopulation, limited water resources, degradation of land, food losses, loss of biodiversity, pests and diseases outbreaks, insufficient distribution channels and policy constraints are the major factors responsible for food insecurity. The intensity of impact from these factors varies from region to region.

2.1 Climate change

Anthropogenic factors such as the combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation and unscientific farming practices are the notable causes of global warming. Frequent and intense floods, heatwaves and other extreme events have become common in recent years. The consequences of climate change are disastrous. Food and water shortages, rising sea levels, frequent wildfires, the rapid spread of pests and diseases are the effects of the ongoing catastrophe (IPCC, 2015).

Agriculture is greatly affected by global climate change since it involves the raising of living plants and animals. The rise in the concentration of CO₂ as well as the temperature increases the host susceptibility of different crops. The magnitude and nature of damage depend on the local agro-ecological situation and management strategies (Thomson et al., 2010). The outbreak of plant diseases can greatly deplete the production, leading to great famines, such as the Irish Famine of the 1840s' (triggered by Late blight of potato) or the Bengal famine of 1940s' (triggered by the brown spot of rice). These could be the lessons to our age, faced with grave threats of climate change, however, armoured with the best of technologies.

The water and temperature stresses on animals can greatly reduce the yield and at times be fatal. The optimum temperature for rearing domestic animals is 10-30⁰ C. And above this temperature, the feeding of animals decreases by 3-5% for every 1⁰ C rise in temperature. In addition to it, the greater temperature reduces the fertility of animals, increase disease incidence and slows growth, leading to low production. (Nelson et al., 2012). A huge change in the dynamics of pests and diseases is observed, for both crops and livestock, due to climate change. The nature and magnitude of the threat depend on the type of management measures and agro-ecological practices adopted to combat this challenge. Since the increase in temperature warms water resources, the aquatic habitats are also affected which is problematic for marine fisheries and aquaculture, in general (Blanchard et al., 2017). The greater burden of climate change is faced by the smallholder farmers as they are completely dependent on agriculture and livestock for their livelihood (IPCC, 2015).

Other impediments to agricultural production include associated challenges like land loss and degradation (due to salt stress, flood and landslide) and irrigation challenges due to hydrological

and meteorological droughts. Climate change can severely curb the biological productivity of soil and disturb its ecological integrity. It degrades the diversity of soil biota, making the soil less fertile. Olsson et al. (2019) has pointed out that agricultural land would shrink dramatically in tropical regions due to the effects of climate change. An elevated level of CO₂ has been linked with the lower nutritional quality of crops. For instance, wheat grown at 546-586 ppm of CO₂ showed lesser protein (5.9-12.7%), lesser zinc (3.7–6.5%) and a lower quantity of iron (5.2–7.5%) than the wheat grown at normal conditions (Shukla et al., 2019). Biofortification of crops using biotechnology could negate these drawbacks and help in ensuring nutritional security.

2.2 Rapid population growth and poverty

The swift increment in global population has elevated the pressure on available resources such as land and water. These have led to over-exploitation of such resources. For instance, fragmentation of cultivable land for settlement purposes has affected food production. Rapid population growth enhances poverty, making people susceptible to hunger. The affordability of available food is linked with the economic standards of the individual. The regional disparity in food distribution and living standards can be attributed to the economic standards of these regions. The data speaks volumes since, of 800 million starving population, many of them are from the poorest regions of the globe. This discrimination should be addressed sooner by international organizations like Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) and World Food Programme (WFP).

2.3 Miscellaneous

The overuse of synthetic pesticides and unsystematic agricultural practices has increased the incidence of pesticide resistance and occasional disease outbreaks. These have posed a great threat to agriculture production and food security. The use of old cultivars and redundant farming practices are also important constraints of agriculture production. Besides production, the challenge lies in the distribution of available food and the nutritional availability of such food. The annual food wastage amounts to 1.6 billion tonnes of which 1.3 billion is edible. Reducing food waste from farm to consumer is necessary to feed the hungry population without increasing the environmental burden of production (Gustavsson et al., 2011).

3. Solution measures

The effects of climate change (higher temperature, precipitation, flooding and extreme events) could be tackled with technological measures (crop improvement, development of new cultivars, improving cropping system, use of digital applications) as well as non-technological approaches (market and land management, change in food consumption pattern) (Howden et al., 2007). The yield of the crops can be maintained by adopting suitable cultivars as per the environment and following the principles of integrated pest and disease management. Sustainable land management and intensification are necessary for greater production. The principles of conservation agriculture and community-based adaptation are useful in the long run (Olsson et

al., 2019). Conservation of soil resources (through conservation tillage, cover cropping, crop rotation, intercropping and mixed cropping) is necessary for sustainable agriculture. Since climate change will continue affecting agricultural production, measures must be taken to minimize the impacts and to maintain food production. In addition, issues of rapid population growth and poverty should be addressed sooner by the concerned authorities.

3.1 Water and soil management

Capturing and storing rainwater and avoiding excess transpiration from soil could minimize the effect of agricultural drought. Better weather forecasting and advanced hydrological modelling could be used to predict the soil moisture content and select the crop variety with maximum water use efficiency (Ravazzani et al., 2017). Smartphone apps, at present, are capable of providing real-time data of crop fields such as soil moisture (using the sensors) and advising farmers to irrigate their fields on time. These technologies have paved a path to precision agriculture (Migliaccio et al., 2015).

Soil degradation should be stopped by reducing the application of synthetic pesticides. Soil moisture should be retained in the field by reducing evapotranspiration loss. This could be achieved using cover crops, reduced tillage and mulching. Amending soil with organic matter preserves its structure and maintains its fertility. Surface runoff can be checked to retain the soil nutrients.

3.2 Use of digital technology

Remote sensing is assisting several agricultural operations like the controlled release of fertilizers, pest and weed management, soil amendment, weather forecasting and crop variety recommendation. This technology will play a key role in modern agriculture by reducing the yield gaps (Hochman et al., 2013). Satellite imaging and digital mapping are also widely used in recent times and have shown promising results in advancing agriculture.

3.3 Conservation of genetic resources

Conservation of genetic resources is essential since farmers, breeders and researchers rely on these to improve the quality and quantity of food production. Any loss of genetic diversity is a threat to the general well-being of the entire world. Preservation of genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants, domesticated animals and their wild relatives is necessary for biotechnological intervention. Genetic intervention in combination with the appropriate management strategies can greatly enhance productivity. This is achieved by the selection of genotypes with greater resource use efficiency and stress tolerance. The novel genetic diversity hence selected is subjected to targeted biotechnology and tools, which could lead to genetic gains. This helps in maximizing the yields. Selective breeding, use of hybrid seeds and genetic modifications have enhanced the productivity of crops, significantly. The necessity of chemical herbicides,

pesticides and antimicrobials has also been reduced as the newly developed crops are more tolerant to a great number of biotic and abiotic stresses.

3.4 Advance biotechnological intervention

Genetic improvement of crops and livestock for heat, drought, disease and pest tolerance is necessary, to increase production. In the past, conventional plant breeding approaches use to play a major role in improving agricultural productivity. The adoption of genetically modified (GM) crops resulted in higher yield, lower pesticide use, improved nutrition and reduction of poverty. However, recent advancements in genome editing have made breeding more powerful. Now, it has become possible to improve the yield attributing characters of crops by altering the endogenous genes rapidly. CRISPER-Cas gene-editing tool has been used extensively with successful results in many crops like rice, wheat, maize, banana, cassava, etc. (Zaidi et al., 2019). The use of transgenic crops has been regulated by different countries since they involve the transfer of foreign DNA (i.e transfer of genetic material from other species or organisms to targeted crops). But genome editing is free from such debate since it involves only the modification of the genome of the concerned organism/ crop. Hence, genome-editing mediated crop improvement is likely to evolve quicker, producing useful crop cultivars with superior productivity and quality.

There are several notable examples of crop varieties developed through such technologies. Water Efficient Maize for Africa (WEMA) project has developed drought-tolerant varieties of maize. Similarly, CRISPR-Cas9-mediated gene-knockout is used in developing high yielding rice, disease-resistant wheat and tomato with enhanced flavour. More advancement in genetic engineering is expected in upcoming decades with precise DNA sequencing, editing, gene replacement; promoter/ regulator based engineering and integrated improvement of multiple traits (stacking) (Sripada et al., 2014; Svitashv et al., 2015). The genome editing technologies will be beneficial in developing disease and pest resistance as well as salt and temperature tolerant cultivars, which are necessary for combating climatic stresses. These technologies are equally useful in animals, leading to greater agricultural output.

Ambitious projects like the development of a highly efficient C4 pathway for photosynthesis (in C3 plants like rice and wheat) are some of the glimpses of future possibilities with biotechnology. Biofortification of crops using the biotechnological procedure could be promising to ensure nutritional security since the nutrient level of crops are affected by CO₂ levels in the atmosphere (the result of climate change), as discussed in earlier sections.

3.5 Climate-smart agriculture

Climate-Smart Agriculture aims to achieve increased productivity with enhanced resilience and reduced greenhouse emissions. This could be the best measure to combat climate change and ensure food security. Climate-resilient food systems are also promising in some parts of the world (Mbow et al., 2014). One example of it is the Direct Seeding practice in Rice i.e. DSR,

which involves the direct sowing of seeds on dry or wet fields, without the necessity of nursery raising (which demands greater water supply.) Adaption of suitable cultivars, optimization of land management practices and sustainable intensification could help in reducing the yield gaps. Management of rainwater (rainwater harvesting) and increasing water use efficiency is necessary to maintain stable production (Shukla et al., 2019). Maintaining the ecosystem is equally important while implementing resilient agricultural productivity to safeguard the environment's sustainability.

3.6 Reducing food wastage:

Care must be taken in the transportation, storage, trade and processing of food to reduce food loss and wastage. This will be equally helpful in the proper distribution of food. One way to minimize food loss is by encouraging the consumption of locally available food which can contribute to food security. Controlling the food loss (pre-and post-harvest) and food waste (amounting 25-30% of total production) could be useful in lessening the disparity of food distribution and ensuring food security. Reducing food loss and food waste to zero might not be possible; however, measures should be taken to reduce food waste by following prevention and management strategies. The principle of 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle) can be applied to ensure lesser food wastage (Bajželj et al., 2014).

3.7 Miscellaneous

The diet of people can be adjusted with new sustainable sources of non-animal protein to increase food security. Pulses are the alternatives to animal products as they are rich in proteins, fibre and micronutrients. Algal biomass and other sea-borne products are currently under test to develop a viable substitute of animal-based protein (Henchion et al., 2017). In some parts of the world, even insects are used as a source of food and feed protein (van Huis & Oonincx, 2017).

Preservation, modification and promotion of indigenous technical knowledge i.e. traditional knowledge could be effective in uplifting food production. Agricultural research and extensions must be prioritized with proper investments and cooperation among national and international organizations. This could enhance the agricultural production capacities, particularly in less developed nations. Innovations such as biological methods of pest control have proven to be effective in solving newer challenges like pesticide resistance.

Food insecurity is likely to increase with climate change. This can be tackled with early warning systems and the development of innovative technology in agriculture. Smallholder farmers are the most vulnerable to climate change since their livelihood depends primarily on agriculture. Efforts must be directed to protect them from the impacts of climate change and to maintain their productivity. Proper market management and policy reforms (economic, political and agricultural policies) at the local and global level would go a long way in making the world food-secure.

Conclusion:

As one of the goals of SDGs under UNO, ending global hunger, achieving food security and improving nutrition is not an overnight project. However, it is plausible in the long run if valiant efforts are made by the concerned parties. Achieving nutritional and food security requires interdisciplinary as well as transdisciplinary approaches. Agricultural science, food science, economics and other social sciences should cooperate with new disciplines such as data science, nanotechnology and artificial intelligence. Right technological intervention in farming practices could ensure food for all and achieve a hunger-free world. It is the right of every global citizen to live a healthy, decent and prosperous life with an abundant supply of nutritious food. Hopefully, the recent advancements in agriculture would be the centerpiece in actualizing these ambitions.

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